

STATE OF THE ART OF QUANTUM COMPUTING: OVERVIEW

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Abstract - In this article, a brief explanation of the operation of quantum computing is presented so that simulations can be presented that exemplify the differences between the processing times of a quantum computer and a classical computer when using the same program. It was used a software that provides a portion of a quantum computer, with a command interface in Python language, in this case Azure Quantum, that was made by IBM, and a classic computer with the Visual Studio Code software for the comparison between processing speeds and efficiency, both being tested with the program that calculates areas of a definite Riemann integral with the trapezoid method.

Keywords: Quantum computing; Quantum mechanics; Azure Quantum; Trapezoid method.

INTRODUCTION

During the 1980s, the American theorist Richard Feynman, with the Russian mathematician Yuri Manin, proposed the fundamental principles of quantum computing, but it was not until 2019, when Google created the first quantum computer, that it was possible to observe new discoveries in the area at a steady pace, with research from IBM and Google and suggesting that soon, manufacture and sell quantum computers with up to 1000 qubits. Although current technological development is sometimes confused with science fiction, much of the general public is unaware of the vast possibilities and benefits that quantum computing can offer. Among some contributions are: the simulation of quantum systems, to determine the behaviors of atoms and molecules in order to adapt and synthesize new medicines, Cybersecurity and password cracking, and also, in the statistical analysis of industrial plants, through the data emitted by the sensors of each equipment, which provides the best predictive maintenance.

For a better understanding of the functionality of quantum computing, it is necessary to understand some of the concepts of quantum mechanics, namely: the spin of the electron, the quantum superposition and its relationship to qubits; In [1] is all the content necessary to establish the connections of quantum physics. In [2] is available the Azure Quantum software platform, which teaches programming from the basic to the advanced level, selected to simulate the capabilities of a quantum computer and run a program based on [3] to make the comparison between the quantum computer and the classical computer. That said, this article gathered theoretical information, simulated and programing, and finally gathered data to

present the current advances and current applications in the area of quantum computing.

DEVELOPMENT

The basis of quantum computing is qubits or quantum bits, and it is different compared to with the classical bits, which contains two states (0 and 1), qubits contain a third state, an entanglement of 0 and 1 state in which it contains a probability of being 0 or 1. The spin of the electron, present in the figure [1], is the property that represents its rotation around its own axis. Since this spin is quantized, this implies that it assumes the values: "up", "down" or both, with the last state resulting from the quantum superposition, which shows that a physical system in our universe can exist in two or more states simultaneously. For this reason, it can be used to portray a qubit, where the *up* takes on a value of 1 and the *down* as 0, which makes it possible for a single electron to be employed to possess a qubit.

Figure [1] – Electron spin.

The quantum computer works with probability, that means that there are both the possibility, right or wrong, with its efficiency depending on the intensity of the wave that represents the result to which it is intended to find. It is due to the probabilistic nature of quantum theory, that unlike the classical computer

(based on a binary system), the only possible error is represented by the user himself, because the machine does not made any mistakes by its own, it only executes what is written in the program that the user made. To decipher the behavior of the spin of the electron and consequently of the qubit, it is essential to use the Schrödinger equation (differential equation) that describes the probabilistic behavior of these subatomic particles, and used to calculate the wave function, so it is possible to describe the quantum state of the particles. The wave function is represented by complex or imaginary numbers, that is, the real value of the wave, that is the probability of finding the particle at a point in space, and the complex value, that shows the phase of the wave. In the same way that it is appropriate for the wave function to be complex, so are the operations done, so the quantum computer works on the basis of imaginary operators. With the study of wave functions, and the relationships between the concatenate of wave and particle it is possible to have a statistical mathematical description of the functioning of these qubits. When the interference is destructive the waves are subtracted, and possibly it is annulled and decreases in as chances of success, however, when it is constructive, the waves are summed, increasing their intensity and consequently, the chance of being found. In other words, the quantum computer probabilistic assumes the best state and adapts the possible answers to approach the most ideal one.

The most advanced quantum computers today are Google's Sycamore and IBM's Eagle, seen in figure [2], both of which have superior processing power to today's classical computers. For example, the 70-qubit Sycamore can perform advanced mathematical operations in milliseconds, which would take a few minutes for a classical computer, depending on the hardware configuration. Another processing capability is that of the Quantum Fourier Transforming (QFT), the quantum analogue of the Fourier form, and can also use qubits and the algorithmic Shor to perform tasks beyond the capacity of others. Classical computers can already perform QFT, but not with such efficiency and agility as the quantum. Quantum computing has some unique algorithms, like Shor's algorithm, which can be used to simplify the factorization of numbers into a product of prime numbers, having the facility to break the RSA algorithm that uses the factorization of the product of two prime numbers in its encryption. And there is also Grover's algorithm, which is a method of quantum encryption and search. The cases are extremely effective for breaking classical computer programs and these algorithms are designed to take advantage of the unique properties of these computers, using the quantum superposition existing in each qubit and its relative uncertainty to perform

advanced calculations more suitably than the classical computer.

Figure [2] – IBM Quantum Computer with Eagle processor.

With the theory established to develop the experiment resorted to the use of the software made available by IBM and Microsoft: Azure Quantum, which provides a small portion of and a quantum computer, through cloud simulation, for the execution of projects and programming without the need download and no computer requirements, only an Internet connection access and a Microsoft account [2]. The software provides a command interface that interacts with the Python or Q# programming language, where it can be used the same type of program that would be made on a classical computer. The Q# language comes from Microsoft Azure itself and is only available to it. Figure [3] shows the Azure Quantum software interface.

Azure Quantum

Introdução ao Azure Quantum. Aprenda, experimente e faça protótipos no hardware quantum atual com Jupyter Notebooks hospedados.

[Introdução](#)

Figure [3] – Azure Quantum initial interface.

For the performance tests with classic computer, the Visual Studio Code 1.72 64-bit programs software was used with the same program. The hardware configurations are as follows: Intel UHD Graphics 630 integrated video card; 8GB of DDR4 2666 MHz RAM; and 2.90 GHz Intel Core i5 10400 processor with 12M cache.

The experiment consisted of two steps: the first dealt with the construction of the programming code, visible in figure [4] and inspired in [3], which calculates areas of a function with definite Riemann integrals with the Trapezoid Method, which was changed from the C# programming language to Python, and also, modified the integral to calculate. With that done, the following function was applied in both programs with the interval between 1 for "a" and 2 for "b":

$$f(x) = \frac{3}{x+2} + 5x^2 - \sqrt{x}$$

The expected result was defined as:

$$\int_1^2 \frac{3}{x+2} + 5x^2 - \sqrt{x} dx$$

$$3 \ln\left(\frac{4}{3}\right) + \frac{233}{12} - \frac{4\sqrt{2}}{3} \cong 18,394$$

The next step was to collect enough data for a didactic analysis. And for this, it was performed from 25000 (twenty-five thousand) to 250000 (two hundred and fifty thousand) trapezoids/iterations in each program and, to have a processing time relationship, a Python library was also added responsible for measuring the exact time the calculation of each program, as you can see at the end of the programming, the figure [4].

```
import time
# Define a função f(x)
def f(x):
    return (3/(x+2)) + (5 * x**3) - (x**(1/2))

# Solicita entrada para a, b e n
a = float(input("Digite a: "))
b = float(input("Digite b: "))
n = int(input("Digite n: "))

start_time = time.time()

# Calcula h
h = (b - a) / n
xi = a
soma = 0
x = 0

c = f(xi)
xi = a + h

print(f'\nx{x}={a:.3f}', end='')
print(f' f(x{x})={c:.3f}', end='')

for i in range(1, n):
    x += h
    c = f(xi)
    soma += c

    print(f'\nx{x}={xi:.3f}', end='')
    print(f' f(x{x})={c:.3f}', end='')
    print(f' soma={soma:.3f}', end='')

    xi += h

c = f(xi)
I = (h / 2) * (f(a) + f(b) + 2 * soma)

print(f'\nx{n}={b:.3f}', end='')
print(f' f(x{n})={c:.3f}', end='')
print(f' soma={soma:.3f}')
print("\n a={:.3f} b={:.3f} n={}".format(a, b, n))
print("(b-a)={:.3f}".format(b - a))
print(" h={:.3f}".format(h))
print(" I={:.3f}".format(I))

end_time = time.time()
execution_time = end_time - start_time
print("\nTempo de execução: {:.6f} segundos".format(execution_time))
```

Figure [4] – Notepad with code written in Python.

The following is the data collected from the result of the classical computer program, seen in Figure [5].

```
a=1.000 b=2.000 n=25000
(b-a)=1.000
h=0.000
I=18.394094806917753
Tempo de execução: 3.253306 segundos
```

Figure [5] – Results obtained by the program on the classical computer.

You must consider the use of Ram memory and CPU processor in other programs that are automatically opened by the user interface. The best consideration is given to the relationship between the calculation time and the number of trapezoids, and the result obtained by the program depends entirely on the hardware of the equipment. Table [1] presents the data collected by the classical computer.

TABLE [1] – Data extracted from the classical computer.

Trapezoids/iteratio ns	Processing Time(s)
25000	3,253305
50000	6,397494
75000	9,846024
100000	11,752231
125000	15,974293
150000	17,706995
175000	20,860651
200000	25,226226
225000	29,660891
250000	29,492737

Note: Trapezoids are the number of divisions made in the area.

In sequence, the data collected from the result of the quantum computer program, seen in figure [6], are displayed.

```
a=1.000 b=2.000 n=25000
(b-a)=1.000
h=0.000
I=18.394094806917753
```

Tempo de execução: 0.462940 segundos

Figure [6] – Results obtained by the quantum computer program.

Just like on the classic computer, it is recommended to consider the available internet network, since it can impact on the result time. The Microsoft Azure software is free, but there is a limitation for data processing of 5 seconds for execution of the program, that is, the efficiency of the software and depends both on the speed of the network connection and the amount

of information that will be processed. Table [2] presents the data collected by the quantum computer.

TABLE [2] – Data extracted from the quantum computer.

Trapezoids/iterations	Processing Time(s)
25000	0,46294
50000	1,106371
75000	1,484475
100000	1,973631
125000	2,474125
150000	3,463775
175000	3,639054
200000	4,119988
225000	4,462622
250000	4,805256

Note: Trapezoids are the number of divisions made in the area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the results collected in tables [1] and [2] it is possible to compare the processing performance of computers, since the quantum computer exceeds or at seven times the processing speed of the conventional computer. For a better contemplation, the graph in Figure [7] illustrates this efficiency comparison well. The "Y" axis represents the necessary time employed in the processing in seconds, while the "X" axis represents the number of iterations in the calculation of trapezoids at each point of analysis. What happens is the remarkable linear progression (in orange) as a function of the time that exists and one computational performance to the other (in blue). It is important to emphasize that the difference in the principles of operation (superposition and statistical mechanics) of the quantum computer allow the same greater optimization and capacity of analysis of complex calculations, that is, what for it is easy to perform, for the classical computer requires a higher level of processing, since it uses the method of comparison (reading, analysis and execution) and factorization (mechanical sequence).

Figure [7] – The graph illustrates the time spent running the classical computer (in blue) and the quantum computer (in orange) in relation to the number of iterations at the points of interest.

There are other methods of comparing performance between the two computers besides the speed in solving simple and complex calculations, as the previous experiment demonstrated. Among them is the comparison of problems N P-completes. On the one hand, the quantum computer finds the result quickly due to the quantum superposition state, whereas it would require a limitation of variables and possibilities for the conventional computer to solve the same problem. The other example that highlights the limitations of one to another is the powerful ability of the quantum computer to analyze and process information, such as extracting from a database, with millions of copies, the specific information of an individual. The classical computer would take you a long time to process the information, i.e. comparing bit by bit. In the case of the quantum computer, by increasing the intensity of the waveform (concatenated wave and particle) that represents the target individual, the chance of identification is dramatically increased within a few seconds.

However, once the computational capabilities are explored in the present article, most of the tasks require the system of operation of the classical computer, and that possibly in the future, will not stop it completely. The greatest advantage of the conventional computer in relation to the quantum is in its ability to work only with what has been programmed to it, works in a linear way and not necessarily required and complex calculations or covers several possibilities, which can condition a lower error rate of the results, because it is something well defined. That said, the emerging evolution of science and technology indicates that both computers will be allies in the process of human technological development, so that one meets the limitations of the other, optimizing processes and generating more precise and efficient solutions in academia and scientific, industrial and cybersecurity.

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